

ARENA Research Unit

Abstract Representations in Neural Architectures

MAX PLANCK INSTITUTE
FOR SOFTWARE SYSTEMS

FIAS Frankfurt Institute
for Advanced Studies

Title: Communication and Engagement Plan

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Communication and Engagement Plan

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Preamble:

The aim of this Communication and Engagement Plan is to briefly point out the strategy that ARENA will follow for its internal communication among projects and team members as well as its external communications and online presence on social media online platforms. It shows the target platforms, target audience, tools as well as communication strategy and objectives.

Internal Communication

This section briefly outlines ARENA's strategy for communication between team members and between projects. It also describes the tools used to keep the team connected, updated and on track.

- **Main objectives:**
 - Keep the team connected and updated
 - Track the projects' progress to ensure that the deadlines are met on time
 - To disseminate projects' outputs among the ARENA team
 - To have the team feedback on the tasks, documents and decisions

- **Targeted audience:**
 - ARENA team members

- **Communication language:**
 - English

- **Communication tools:**
 - Online chat; Discord
 - Email; ARENA mailing list, update emails from project coordinator,...
 - Data Sharing platforms; GitHub, Hessianbox, Zenodo community
 - Online meetings; monthly projects meetings, Journal club, and early career researchers meeting

External Communication

In this section, we provide a brief overview of ARENA's objectives for external communication. We explain our approach to reaching a wider range of audience by targeting relevant online platforms and communication strategy.

- **Main objectives:**
 - To disseminate scientific activities, outputs, and achievements of ARENA
 - To communicate scientific activities and related events of neuroscience, cognitive psychology, computer science and other related communities.

- Have open scientific discussions
- **Targeted audience:**
 - National and international scientists
 - Society (public) national/international
- **Communication language:**
 - English
- **Communication platforms:**
 - ARENA website
 - Social network; Twitter/X
 - Blogs, national press and other relevant European and international press; The Decoder, DFG Magazine, EU Research, ...
- **Communication strategy:**
 - Branding strategy:
 - Affiliated to broad topics e.g. #neuroscience, #psychology
 - ARENA specific topics e.g. #NeuralArchitecture, #AbstractRepresentation, ...
 - ARENA Logo
 - Colour template
 - Networking strategy:
 - ARENA website
 - Project profiles with explicit link to partners
 - Publications with explicit link to team members
 - Selected publications to prepare a press release for the website including a key figure
 - Submit news pieces + figures link to the ARENA website
 - Twitter/X
 - Follow and reflect partners
 - Follow and reflect lab members
 - Follow and reflect relevant national and international events, news within the broad and specific hashtags
 - Tweet selected publications + tag partners, funding agency, ... link to the ARENA website
 - Tweet project news + tag partners, funding agency, ... link to the ARENA website
 - Tweet ARENA news, such as new members, ... link to the ARENA website
 - **Targets:**
 - Short-term (2023)
 - At least 1 tweet per week

- At least 2 updates per month on the website, e.g. project news, publications, ...
- Regular retweets

- Mid-term (2024 - 2025)
- Long term (2026 and beyond)

- Implementation plan for short-term targets:
 - Review and finalise the communication concept and the short term targets
 - Update the twitter handler profile with broad and specific hashtags
 - Setup a twitter feed pipeline including responsibilities
 - Setup the website updates pipeline including responsibilities
 - Prepare an evaluation report for the short-term targets
 - Revise mid-term targets and prepare the implementation plan